

Help sheet: Manufacturing

explanatory notes:

the following explanations can help you find the right option, if you are unsure.

I have my own smartphone or similar device.

If your smartphone brand is not listed, please select option C (2 blocks).

I use this device ...

It's easy to underestimate how much time you spend at your phone. However, most smartphones today allow you to check your daily usage time in the settings.

The smartphone's power saving mode is ...

Activating power saving mode not only conserves your smartphone battery, but also other resources by reducing data transmission through the deactivation of background processes.

When the device is no longer needed, I will ...

If you haven't thought about this yet, just take a moment to consider what you did with your last smartphones.